

ADIGRAT UNIVERSITY

**COLLEGE OF BUSINESS AND ECONOMICS
DEPARTMENT OF MANAGEMENT**

**EFFECT OF MICROFINANCE ON THE LIVELIHOOD OF WOMEN: A CASE OF
DEDEBIT CREDIT AND SAVINGS INSTITUTION IN GANTA-AFESHUM DISTRICT,
EASTERN ZONE, TIGRAY, ETHIOPIA**

**A THESIS SUBMITTED TO DEPARTMENT OF MANAGEMENT IN PARTIAL
FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEGREE OF THE MASTERS IN
BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION (MBA)**

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ADIGRAT, ETHIOPIA

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DECLARATION

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ADCS	Adigrat Diocesan Catholic Secretariat
ARD	Agricultural and Rural Development
AEMFI	Association of Ethiopia micro finance Institutions
CSA	Central Statistical Agency
DFID	Department for International Development ()
DECSI	Dedebit Credit and Saving Institution
FAO	Food and Agriculture organization
HEPM	Household Economic Portfolio Model
IFAD	International Fund for Agricultural Development
MFI	Microfinance Institution
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
REST	Relief Society of Tigray
SLA	Sustainable Livelihood Approach
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
TLU	Tropic Livestock Unit
UNDP	United Nations Development Program
WOoARD	Woreda of Agriculture and Rural Development

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ABSTRACT

Poor households participate in microfinance institutions in the expectation that the credit will improve their livelihood, however, the effect of microfinance on the poor remains an intensely debate issue. For instance in the study conducted Mekelle city, Gosa (2014) in his study conducted in Mekelle city noted that DECSI is helping poor households to invest in better nutrition, housing, health, and education, the households especially the women's access to credit is still insufficient due to interest rates burden. The objective of this study was to assess effect of microfinance on the livelihood of women a case of Dedebit Credit and Savings Institution in five Tabias of Ganta-Afeshum district, Eastern Tigray. The study employed combination of purposive and convenient sampling methods for to select tabias while random sampling for respondents. The overall process includes collection of survey data from women household clients before and after accessing DECSI credit scheme and comparison was made using the DFID Sustainable Livelihood Approach. Accordingly 258 out of 724 women clients and 5 loan officers of DECSI were selected. The study employed both primary and secondary sources of data. The survey data were collected through structured questionnaire from the women beneficiaries and this is supplemented by semi-structured interview with loan officers. The secondary data on the other hand were obtained from the annual reports of the MFI, government reports and other relevant materials. The paired t-test was applied to assess the effect of the program on the livelihood of its clients. The findings reveal that women clients of DECSI have a significantly higher average livelihood asset after accessing credit than prior to joining the program. The survey result reveals that DECSI microfinancing scheme has a positive impact on the clients overall household income, household assets, housing and property improvements, access to education, and access to health facilities. I could be argued that the provision of financial resources has significant positive effects on household livelihood outcomes. However, there is much variability in the nature and magnitude of the effect, which is mainly due to the influence of the macro environment, financial products and terms of the in DECSI. Therefore, to bring about sustainable development and to reduce poverty in the region more practical and sound policy should be formulated in order to improve the magnitude of impact. Moreover, all development stakeholders should work together with the microfinance programs.

Key Words: Women household livelihood, Micrifinanace credit scheme, loan repayment

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the Study

The poor substantially benefit from access to small-scale financial resources such as credit and savings. Where available, these and other financial services help low-income people improve their livelihood, create and expand microenterprises, increase productivity, smooth income and consumption flows, enlarge and diversify their income sources, and thus improve their welfare. Therefore, improving access to finance, especially access to credit by providing small loans, is considered as a necessary condition to reduce poverty since it contributes to strengthen the poor's productive assets including their human capital (Arouri et al., 2014). Recognizing the problem of market imperfections in the formal financial sector of developing countries, microfinance was introduced in the 1970s by the Grameen Bank in Bangladesh (Armendariz and Morduch, 2005). Since then the provision of micro financial resources has been advocated as an effective poverty alleviation and development tool.

Microfinance is widely considered as one of the crucial development industry that provides financial and nonfinancial services to a large size of poor people. The effectiveness of microfinance industry is dependent on its impact on poverty reduction and socioeconomic development and its ability to continue growing. Generally microfinance known as a provision of a wide range of financial services such as small loan, savings, insurance, deposit and payment services to poor and low-income households who are deprived from accessing to conventional financial services for lack collateral (Jonsonand Rogaly, 1997). These services are provided for a productive purpose of start-up new businesses or extend businesses which are the source of sustainable livelihood (Lakwo, 2007).

British Department for International Development (DFID) defines sustainable livelihood as "A livelihood comprises the capabilities, assets (including both material and social resources) and activities required for a means of living. A livelihood is sustainable when it can cope with and recover from stresses and shocks, maintain or enhance its capabilities and assets, while not undermining the natural resource base"). Sustainable livelihood approach provides a framework through which gender relations can recursively be studied from people's own livelihood practices. It is an approach that builds on people-centeredness taking into account what they have and do as agents for, rather than victims of, their own

change. Therefore, the approach recognizes five assets or capitals namely human: physical, social, financial, and natural. These assets comprise the portfolio of the household out of which they construct their living (DFID, 1999 as cited in Tsehaye, 2007). The link of microfinance with sustainable livelihood framework helps to assess how microfinance supports rural livelihoods by supplementing and strengthening the five assets or capital owned by the household (Mago, 2014).

Microfinance is the provision of financial services, such as loans, savings, insurance, money transfers, and payments facilities to low income groups. Loans are supposed to be used for productive purposes such as investments, seeds or additional working capital for micro enterprises. On the other hand, it could be used to provide for immediate family expenditure on food, education, housing and health. Microfinance is an effective way for poor people to increase their economic security and thus reduce poverty. It enables poor people to manage their limited financial resources, reduce the impact of economic shocks and increase their assets and income (Robinson, 2001). Microfinance is no longer an experiment or a wish, it is a proven success. It has worked successfully in many parts of the World – Africa, Asia, Latin-America, Europe and North America. It is safe and profitable; indeed it is the oldest and most resilient financial system in history. The key issues in Microfinance include the realization that poor people need a variety of financial services, including loans, savings, money transfer and insurance which Microfinance provides. It is a powerful tool to fight poverty through building of five basic assets and serving as an absorber against external ties and financial shocks. Microfinance involves building of financial sub-system which serves the poor and its architecture could be easily integrated into the financial system of the nation.

Wolday (2000) argued that the establishment of sustainable and profitable microfinance institutions that reach a large number of poor household who are not served by the conventional banks such as, commercial and development banks because of high collateral and other security requirement, their institutional and structural problems have been the current issue of the new development strategy of the Ethiopian government, that is poverty reduction strategy. Since the takeover of the present government in 1991, considerable attempt has been made to liberalize the financial sector. To this effect, Proclamation No. 84/94 was issued, which allows private domestic investors to participate in banking and insurance activities, which were previously monopolized by the government. However, the issuance of this proclamation alone did not totally solve the financial problem of the

economically active poor people in rural and urban areas (Seifu, 2012).

Based on the development of the microfinance industry at national and global level, Ethiopia took the direction of building sustainable microfinance institution in order to deliver financial services to the poor. Microfinance was first seen in Ethiopia in the late 1980s, offered mostly by NGO relief and development programs. The year 1996 saw the formalization of the industry with the government issued “Proclamation for licensing and supervision of microfinance institutions No 40/1996 (Wolday, 2000). This Directorate officially brought MFIs under Ethiopia’s monetary and financial framework. It enabled all MFIs to accept deposits and stressed the need for sound commercial principles in the sector.

Ethiopian microfinance has made remarkable progress over past decades. In Ethiopia there are over 27 microfinance institutions, reaching over 1.8 million clients in a country of about 80 million populations. However, it should be noted that twenty seven microfinance institutions meet only less than 20% of the demand for the financial service of the active poor (AEMFI, 2008).

In Tigray there are different governmental and nongovernmental microfinance/micro credit institutions working in financial services. Out of which Dedebit Credit and Saving Institution (DECSI) is one of the largest micro finance institutions in Ethiopia that serve about 425,172 clients throughout Tigray, with more than 4.3 million populations, 38% of the DECSI borrowers are women. In terms of outreach DECSI is the second largest microfinance in Ethiopia. Nevertheless, the depth of outreach to the poorest (core poor) is not yet acceptable (AEMFI, 2008).

DECSI is helping the poor, particularly women; help themselves by creating access to different financial services in the rural and urban areas of Tigray mainly aimed at enhancing its client's welfare and improving their standard of living. Loan, savings and pension services are the main products offered by the institution (Wolday, 2002). However, it is tend to be inconclusive whether DECSI’s intervention is leading to success as Asmelah (2003) argued that the effect of this particular microfinance on the wellbeing of rural households was not significant. Therefore, this study focused on assessing effect of microfinance on the livelihood of women in Ganta-Afeshum Woreda, Tigray.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Despite a multitude of studies devoted to the topic, the effect of microfinance programs on the

poor in developing countries remains an intensely debate issue, for example, Sachs (2009) in his research found that microfinance may not be appropriate in every situation especially as one size fit all strategy in poverty alleviation and empowerment. He explained that the poor governance infrastructure, dispersed population in the rural areas and gender inequalities hinder the potential benefits of microfinance in Africa.

Aguilar (2006) reported that farmers who borrow from microfinance institutions were no better off than those who did not borrow. Alfred (2007) found that microfinance does not in itself empower women. Rather, it provides a catalyst for women clients to (re)create for themselves acceptable social spaces within their hitherto hegemonic gender relations. Such a contention also stem from the emerging questions on the usual optimism with which development and or microfinance interventions are evaluated by taking beneficiaries as mere recipients of interventions. Yet, they too partake in the transformation of interventions into an acceptable and meaningful life in line with their contextual aspirations. Moreover, Wright (2000) states that much of the skepticism of MFIs stems from the argument that microfinance projects fail to reach the poorest, generally have a limited effect on income drive women into greater dependence on their husbands and fail to provide additional services desperately needed by the poor. In addition, Wright says that many development practitioners not only find microfinance inadequate, but that it actually diverts funding from more pressing or important interventions such as health and education.

Though micro finance institutions have enabled low income women in their registered groups to acquire affordable loans without little or collaterals requirement, they are faced by many challenges which make their livelihood sustainability very difficult (Armendariz and Morduch, 2005).

In Ethiopia even though microfinance programs have been considered increasingly as important safety nets of the poor, knowledge about the achievements of these strategies remains only partial and limited, generally in the case of rural setting (Tolera, 2017). Similarly in the study conducted Mekelle city, Gosa (2014) noted that Dedibit microfinance is helping poor households to move from hand to mouth survival to invest in better nutrition, housing, health, and education, the households especially the women's access to credit is still insufficient due to interest rates burden.

Poor households participate in microfinance institutions in the expectation that borrowing will increase their income, smoothen consumption, enhance their food security, sustain self

employment, reduce the risk of vulnerability, increase savings, strengthens the basis for human capital formation, etc. And different studies have been conducted on the stated subject. This study specifically intended to enhance our understanding by proving or disproving existing findings in the study area. In light of this context, the purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of microfinance on the livelihood of women.

1.3. Basic Research Questions

In the course of the study, the following basic questions were raised and answered.

1. How microfinance contribute to improving the livelihood and well-being of the women or otherwise?
2. What effect does access to microfinance has on raising the women's participation in household decision?
3. What are the challenges faced by women in repayment of loans from microfinance?

1.4. Objective of the Study

1.4.1. General Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study was to investigate the effect of microfinance on the livelihood of women a case of Dedebit credit and savings institution in Ganta-Afeshum district, Eastern Tigray.

1.4.2. Specific objectives of the Study

The study was guided by the following objectives

4. To analyze the contributions of microfinance to improving or otherwise the livelihoods and wellbeing of women
5. To examine the effect of microfinance on raising the women's participation in household decision-making.
6. To identify the challenges faced by the women in repayments of loans borrowed from the microfinance.

1.5. Significance of the Study

The study can provide basic information on the effect of micro finance program in improving the life of rural women. The results of the study can be important in providing insight for policy makers and microfinance institutions found at different levels. Microfinance plays a great role in

the lives of millions of poor people particularly women as it acts as a way of improving their livelihood. In this regard the study may help women to understand how microfinance institutions affects their livelihoods and be able to take advantages of the microfinance programs to improve themselves economically, socially as well as politically. Finally, it will be used as central and initial point for further research.

1.6. Delimitation of the Study

The focus of the study was mainly on assessing the effect of microfinance on the livelihoods of households before after credit access.. This study was limited to the women in the five Tabias¹ of Ganta-Afeshum District, in Eastern Tigray, namely Beati – Maymesanu, Bukot –Nehebi, Dibla – Seit, Golah – Genahiti and Sassun –Beithariat who were participating in the microfinance credit scheme of DECSI. Therefore it may not have a scientific justification to assure the readers that the final conclusion out of this paper could be representative and applicable to all households who are participating in microfinance programs throughout the country. The study was limited to the women household accessed credit for four years by the time of the research and its effects on women livelihood.

1.7. Limitation of the Study

The study was limited to the women who were taking credit loan in group and individually from DECSI. Hence, generalization of some facts and findings of the study were limited to the specific institution considered in the undertaking of the study.

A large sample size made up of different microfinance institutions from the Woredas² in the Tigray region could have allowed for generalizations of the findings. Nevertheless, the study limited only to the Ganta-Afeshum Woreda missed such opportunity due to financial and time constraints.

Also, obtaining the necessary data was hard. This can be explained by the fact that I was forced to get a permission letter from the head office in Mekelle and had to go to the selected sample tabias, making it time consuming because of the relatively poor transportation service negatively affecting the study time schedule.

The study assessed effect of microfinance on the livelihood of established DECSI women

¹ Tabia: is the lowest administrative unit in Ethiopia.

² A woreda is a district or local administrative unit managed by a local government

clients before and after loan access comparison excluding new clients as control group. Thus the current findings may overestimate the effect of the DECSI program.

1.8. Organization of the Thesis

The research paper was organized in five chapters. Chapter one covered the introductory part of the study. Chapter two dealt with an overview of both the existing literature and internal studies in the area and draws upon key themes within the literature which inform the study. It also contained the conceptual framework. Chapter three dealt with the design and methodology of the research. Chapter four was about an overview of data analysis, representation, interpretation and discussion. Finally, chapters five was about the summary, conclusion and recommendations of the study.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Introduction

This Chapter explored the various literature related to the effect of access to micro financial resources on household particularly women livelihood outcomes. The chapter is divided into two sections namely: the theoretical and the empirical literature review.

The theoretical literature section reviewed meanings and concepts regarding microfinance and livelihood conceptual approaches and the link between the provision of microfinance and livelihood development. It explored the different pathways by which access to microfinance resources can have effect on household livelihood assets and outcome. It further explored common challenges that rural household clients of MFI face during loan repayment.

The empirical literature part presented the various evidences on the empirical effect of microfinance on household livelihood outcomes. The section presents empirical evidence on the different effects of micro-financial resources under various assets of human, natural, social, physical, financial and methodological grounds...

2.2. Theoretical Literature

2.2.1. Definitions and Concept of Microfinance

Microfinance is the provision of financial services to low income poor and very poor self-employed people. Microfinance covers a package of financial services including loans, savings, insurance, leasing, transfers and social intermediation provided by formal, semi-formal and informal institutions (Robinson, 2001).. Schreiner, (2001) support this view by defining microfinance as “the attempt to improve access to small deposits and small loans for poor households neglected by banks.”

It is important to note that Edgecomb and Barton (1998) and Sievers and Vandenberg (2007) explain that ‘social intermediation’ includes non-financial support provided to prospective borrowers to help them to acquire skills and values, which they need to initiate and sustain their microenterprises. This involves training in credit norms and procedures, savings discipline, business management, technical skills, business counseling, marketing information and assistance, product development, appropriate technology development and transfer, and the development of organizations of micro-entrepreneurs. Microfinance

institutions (MFIs) which encompass a wide range of providers that vary in legal structure, mission and methodology, offer these financial services to clients who do not have access to mainstream bank or other formal financial service providers (Adjei, et al, 2009).

The new thinking embraces services for women, children, and the poorest of the poor. Steel and Anda (2003), defined microfinance as small financial transactions with low income household and micro enterprises, both urban and rural, using non-standardized methodologies like character based lending, group guarantees and short term repeat loans. Microfinance refers to loans, savings, insurance, transfer services, microcredit loans and other financial products targeted at low-income clients. Microfinance has been changing the lives of people and revitalizing communities worldwide since the beginning of time.

2.2.2. Microfinance and Livelihood Development

The provision of financial resources is not an end in itself. It is a means to achieve a specific objective such as livelihood development. Microfinance enables households to mobilise and harness their resources and optimally exploit the opportunities available to them. Private and local resources are the foundation for household and community development. It is believed that resources at the disposal of households are the basis for their livelihood development. Microfinance brings a positive change in household livelihoods through its production and consumption effects as well as its social effects in empowering women and promoting the culture of entrepreneurship (Ziaul, 2014).

Access to small financial resources encourages the expansion of existing or setting up new non-farm microenterprises by mobilising and putting up together the resources owned by the household. Microfinance also improves agricultural productivity by adopting productivity enhancing methods and inputs thus increasing yields per hectare. Therefore, financial resources used for investment purposes increase production and income for the household and positively contributing to the local economy. According to FAO (2000), an increase in income in turn, will have a multiplied effect on the quantity, composition, and timing of consumption, saving, and asset holding. The acquisition of new assets and improvement and consolidation of the existing ones along with increased income ensures consumption stability, food security and strengthens economic security. Through its effect on household livelihood and local economic development, microfinance can also have positive repercussion effects on natural resources. By relaxing the dependence and pressure of the rural poor on natural resources and promoting diversification of alternative economic activities, microfinance can

have beneficial impacts on environmental sustainability.

According to Dunn (1996), loans from microfinance institutions provide an additional financial resource in the current period to be allocated to any or all of the households activities. The proportion of household loan that is actually allocated to various activities depends on several factors, including available economic opportunities, economic and social constraints, joint and individual preferences, as well as intra-household decision making dynamics.

The term livelihood is often used interchangeably with strengthening economic empowerment and refers generally to economic production, employment, and household income. A more holistic understanding of livelihood, however, incorporates a broader context of economic development, reduced vulnerability, and environmental sustainability. The value added by a sustainable livelihoods approach to microfinance is its focus on households' capabilities, assets and vulnerability, and how rural micro financing can play a part in enhancing people's livelihood strategies and outcomes. It offers the opportunity to examine the role that targeted microfinance services can play in raising rural households' resource endowments and capitals in a sustainable and meaningful way (Amine, 2016).

Formal financial institutions tend to be reluctant to extend financial resources to the poor and vulnerable rural household, primarily engaged in smallholder farming. Some of the reasons include, dispersed demand for financial sector, low economic activity, high information and transaction costs, weak institutional capacity, seasonality of agricultural activity, and lack of usable collateral. For these reasons, targeting them is usually considered too costly and carries high risks in the form of default and non-repayment. Nevertheless, history and experience proved that the rural poor households constitute a substantial part of microfinance institutions' potential client base in the developing countries (CGAP, 2003). Hence, adopting a sustainable livelihoods approach can contribute to the understanding of microfinance institutions on the specific needs and priorities of potential clients who are otherwise not considered bankable by main stream financial institutions. Such understanding is not only central to the analysis of impact but also crucial for microfinance institutions to develop appropriate microfinance products and lending strategies that respond to small farmers' real needs and capacities (Mago, 2014).

Microfinance enables rural households to have control over their assets and environment. As a result they become capable of defending themselves against impoverishment as they engage

in coping strategies for their livelihoods. Access to finance makes them to engage in risky but potentially profitable economic activities that are likely to make them wealthy. The poor are thereby empowered to pull themselves out of poverty and the vicious cycle of poverty transforms to a virtuous cycle of positive livelihoods outcomes (Mago, 2014:558).

Accesses to financial resources also reduce households' vulnerability by providing means to cope with emergency needs during seasonal changes and market fluctuations. It also helps to prevent households from selling their productive assets in times of low cash flows thereby increasing the economic security of the household without compromising their asset base in the long-run. Furthermore, the household can improve its social capital through its participation in solidarity group loans, and establish mutual trust and reciprocity. In addition, household members may experience a rise in self-esteem, dignity and a sense of empowerment through opportunities provided by access to financial services. Therefore, the provision of micro financial resources can directly or indirectly contribute to strengthening of the livelihood assets and activities which constitute a center stage in the livelihood approach.

The accumulation of productive and business assets, the improvement in human capital through training, education, and nutrition, the protection against risks and shocks as well as the creation of employment opportunities contribute to increased income which will ultimately leads into more consumption (welfare) and more savings. Moreover, increased level of income will enable clients to successfully repay their loans and eventually diversify their livelihood strategies (Amine, 2016).

2.2.3. Effect of Microfinance on Livelihoods of Women

Essentially the primary targets of microfinance programs are women who are often marginalized in many aspects in the developing countries. Microfinance programs are often in favour of women clients who are, for the most part, excellent clients. Several studies identified social benefits that women gain from participating in microfinance programs. They feel less marginalized, have higher aspiration for their children's education and future, use more reliable source of drinking water, are more likely to use latrines and contraceptives, and are less likely to marry at an early age (Webster and Fidler, 1996).

The effect of MF on livelihoods is focused in terms of the changes to livelihoods assets and the use of livelihood assets to cope with vulnerability. The provision of MFI can assist the poor find the means to protect their livelihoods against shocks and to build up and diversify their livelihood activities (Johnson & Rogaly, 1997). Chowdhury & Bhuiya (2004) argued

that if MF is to fulfill its social objectives of bringing financial services to the poor, it is important to know the extent to which its wider impacts contribute to poverty reduction. Social networks play an important part in helping clients escape from poverty. Access to social networks provides clients with a defense against having to sell physical and human assets and so protect household assets.

2.2.4. The Challenges during Repayment of Loans

A borrower of a financial institution is expected to payback a principal plus an interest periodically and problems of loan repayment are not rare occurrences. In this regard, Fitsum (2014) identified the major challenges that hinder the repayment performance process in both lender and borrower side. Those are unavailability of grace period, shortage of loan repayment period, insufficient loan size, informal lenders and weak follow-up to utilize loan. In addition to this there are internal and external factors the institution faces, some of them are: - lack of own office, turnover of employee, shortage of cash fund and improper influence of the third part in loan disbursement and approval are major ones.

Norell (2001) also list four reasons why rural household clients' face challenges in repayment of loans as follows:-

- a. Clients often test the MFI to see if it is serious about collecting loan payments on time. They may know MFI staffs are not so responsible to shareholders to make a profit.
- b. Client's lives are often full of unpredictable crises, such as illness or death of family members. They feel compelled to provide financial help, even if the funds are borrowed from the MFI.
- c. If loans are too large for the cash needs of the business, extra funds may go toward personal use. When the loan needs to be repaid, the client cannot pay back the loan without recapitalizing the business.
- d. If loan are given on the basis of favoritism, clients may attempt to delay payment or default. They often hope that their friend in the MFI will encourage the organization to cancel the loan rather than take the clients to court or seize their property.

2.2.5. Conceptual Approach

Households in rural areas own certain assets and engage the activities geared towards the market and others for home consumption (Sebstad *et al.*, 1995).. An approach that integrates assets and their outcomes in the process of production and consumption is, therefore,

important to understand the patterns of resource mobilisation and allocation decisions of the household. In the context of an integrated approach, microfinance is assumed to complement the resource owned by the household particularly their financial resources (Alia, et al, 2014). Commonly two approaches namely the Household Economic Portfolio Model (HEPM) and the Sustainable Livelihood Approach (SLA) that place the household at the center of livelihood analysis are used to conceptualize and interpret the findings of a study. These two approaches link how microfinance could contribute to household livelihoods. SLA was adopted in this study.

2.1.5.1 The Household Economic Portfolio Model (HEPM)

The HEPM is a dynamic conceptual model developed by Chen and Dunn (Marr, 2002) and it explains the interactions among a bundle of resources, economic activities and the circular flows between them.

The model presents a set of links whereby resources affect economic activities and each effect becomes a cause in its own right generating further effects (Al-Al-Mamun, et al, 2011). The approach looks at the household, and its economic activity and the local society in which it is embedded and traces the interaction among them.

Government policies and regulations on interest rate, exchange rate, import duties, taxes and subsidies have important implications on the operation of microfinance institutions as well as their clients. External contextual factors also determine patterns of behaviour in a society. Institutions determine access and allocation of productive resources, safety networks, negotiations and relations and exert positive or negative influence on the operations of microfinance clients and institutions. Therefore, understanding institutional processes and mechanisms allows the identification of constraints and opportunities to household livelihoods (Scoones, 2005).

2.1.5.2 The sustainable livelihood approach (SLA)

Sustainable Livelihood Approach (SLA) used as an organizing framework to explain and understand the livelihood resources, strategies and activities at household. Livelihood Framework was strongly promoted by the Department for International Development (DFID), the British State Development Cooperation Agency (De Haan, 2012:346; Mago, 2014). The central element of the sustainable livelihood approach proposed by DFID is that its analytical structure makes it easy to understand how the various factors such as the

vulnerability context, household assets, and institutions affect livelihood outcomes, and show how each of these factors relate to each other.

In rural areas of the developing countries, the household is considered to be the basic unit of production and consumption given its physical, financial, human, and social and natural resources at its disposal. Within the livelihood approach, a household has been described as “a site in which particularly social and economic interdependencies occur between groups of individuals with diverse preferences” (Ellis, 2000). Poor people exercise a variety of innovative activities in their effort to survive difficult situations. The resources and entitlements at their disposal determine to a large extent their coping capacity.

Fouracre, (2001) argues that “a policy of sustainable rural livelihoods focuses not on the needs of the rural people, but rather, builds on the existing assets of the poor, both at the village and individual level”. Cahn (2002) further notes that the SLA focuses on what people have rather what they do not have. Therefore, the approach recognizes five assets or capitals namely human: physical, social, financial, and natural. These assets comprise the portfolio of the household out of which they construct their living. Regarding the importance of livelihood assets, and deriving from SLA’s approach, Moser and Dani (2008) suggest that “assets are the resource endowments and capabilities that sustain and enhance people’s livelihoods”. The type and amount of each asset that a household holds is a function of past investment and accumulation strategies and activities, which in turn are shaped by social, cultural, political and economic opportunities and constraints.

Within the context of SLA framework, the provision of financial resources such as microfinance, promotes access and entitlements as well as strengthens household assets. The link of microfinance with sustainable livelihood framework helps to assess how microfinance supports rural livelihoods by supplementing and strengthening the five assets or capital owned by the household (Mago, 2014).

Rural households in order to manage as well as improve their livelihood, they pursue a “livelihood strategy” that may comprise a number of different activities such as farming, herding, fishing, off-farm employment and the exploitation of natural resources through hunting and gathering with the objective of income generation, risk reduction, food security, sustainable management of natural resources. In order to engage in these activities, households mobilise the assets at their disposal (Mago, 2014).

In general, a livelihood activity is said to be sustainable when it can cope with and recover from stresses and shocks and maintain or enhance its capabilities and assets both now and in the future, while not undermining the natural resource base (Krantz, 2001). Any activity that undermines the household's long-term productive potential is thus considered to be unsustainable.

Below is a diagrammatic representation of the Sustainable Livelihood Framework used by DFID.

Figure 2.1: Sustainable Livelihoods Framework. Graph from DFID (1999).

The above framework portrays the different mechanisms through which livelihood assets, strategies, and outcomes are interlinked in a given contextual and vulnerability contexts. The vulnerability context is affected by external factors which are outside the control of households. The interrelationships among the various factors will determine livelihood opportunities in a positive or negative way. The livelihood outcomes expressed in terms of increased income, improved well-being, reduced vulnerability, improved food security and sustainable management of natural resources are the products of the five principal assets or capital and the strategies pursued to combine them (Alinovi, et al, 2010).

UNDP (2017) put an analysis of different types of capital as follows:

- a. Human Capital: It represents the abilities, experience, work skills and the physical state of good health which, when combined, allow populations to engage with different strategies and fulfill their own objectives for their livelihoods.

- b. Social Capital: It refers to the social resources, which populations will rely on when seeking their objectives relating to livelihoods (in the present study this refers specifically to local social capital, this being networks, associations, local authorities, local officials and broader population receiving program assistance).
- c. Natural Capital: It is the term used to refer to the stocks of naturally occurring resources (soil, water, air, genetic resources, etc.) which can be used as inputs to create additional benefits, such as food chains, protection against soil or coastal erosion, and other natural resources which can support livelihoods.
- d. Physical Capital: This refers to the basic infrastructure and production inputs needed to support livelihoods.
- e. Financial Capital: This refers to the financial resources which populations employ to achieve their objectives regarding livelihoods.

The framework also shows that policies, institution and processes that are part of the wider context affect livelihood assets and outcomes. They determine who gains access to which type of asset, and define what range of livelihood strategies is open and attractive to people (Krantz, 2001). Livelihood assets are transformed into livelihood strategies through the mediation of institutions and organisations embedded in the laws, policies as well as cultural norms of a given community (Alinovi, et al, 2010).

2.3. Review of Empirical Literature

2.3.1. Global Experience

A study of 16 different MFIs from all over the world pointed out that having access to MF services have led to an enhancement in the quality of life of clients, had increased their self confidence, and had helped them diversify their livelihood security strategies and thereby increase their income (Robinson, 2001). Wright (2000) stated that from the little research that has been conducted on the impact of MF interventions on health and education, nutritional indicators seem to improve where MFIs have been working. MF interventions have been shown to have a positive impact on the education of clients' children because one of the first things that poor people do with new income from micro-enterprise activities are to invest in their children's education (Littlefield, et al, 2003).

Studies made in Grameen Bank in 1995 show that Microfinance has a positive impact on savings and capital accumulation and as a result the investment was higher for long time borrowers than for newer one to the extent 260 percent as compared to non-members.

Microfinance in Grameen Bank has also resulted in greater involvement of members in income generating activities compared to the control groups (Hulme & Mosley, 2003).

Dupas and Robinson (2013:163-164) in their study on saving constraints and microenterprise development examined the effect of access to micro savings on business investment in Kenya using randomized study approach. Women who were market vendors participated in the study. The findings revealed that treated women were found to actively use the saving account opened for them and their average saving increased. The readiness of women vendors to use banking services that did not pay out any interest indicates that they were having problems on accessing saving facilities. Women vendors not only increased their saving but also investment to expand business activities has increased significantly relative to the untreated control group.

Hulme & Mosley (2003) also noted that every loan made to a woman contributes to the strengthening of the economic and social position of women. MF projects can reduce the isolation of women as when they come together in groups they have an opportunity to share information and discuss ideas and develop a bond that was not there previously. However, Chowdhury & Bhuiya (2004) found that violence against women actually increased when women joined the program, as not all men were ready to accept the change in power relations, and so resorted to violence to express their anger.

CARE Tanzania (2006) also did study on village savings and Loans and women's Empowerment Strategic Impact Inquiry in Tanzania using a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods. The study found that there was an increase in education expenditure, greater food security and health, increase in self- confidence and role in decision making among members.

2.3.2. Ethiopian experience

A recent study by Tsehay and Mengistu (2002) revealed that 84 percent of frequent rural women clients and 62.9 percent of frequent urban women clients have shown significant improvement in their household income. The authors concluded that access to microfinance positively contributed to ownership of additional household assets, which are important for empowering women clients economically. One major indicator of household welfare is residence house and same authors indicated that 60 percent of urban clients and 18.3 percent of rural clients made repairs to their houses. Similarly the authors concluded that MFIs intervention resulted in improving household diet.

Teferi (2002) in his study on DECSI found that DECSI's program has had a positive impact on the livelihoods of its clients. Compared to non-clients, clients have experienced greater improvements in terms of income, consumption and assets. They also seem to be more food secure and less vulnerable to shocks and have a greater diversification in terms of income sources. The study found that the improvement in economic condition of the clients is a necessary condition for DECSI's program that could lead to social and political empowerment for the marginalized groups. The study also concluded that economic empowerment leads to social and political empowerment.

In the study made on DECSI Solomon (2013) identified significant determinants of loan repayment performance were level of education, income financed from the loan, loan size and number of times borrowed. All of these factors increase the probability of loan repayment. Even though they are insignificant, availability of another loan, loan diversion, and number of dependents, medical expenses and celebrating social ceremonies reduce the loan repayment performance.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

The research method part discussed site selection and description, the research design, sources of data, sampling techniques, instruments of data gathering, and methods of data analysis consecutively.

3.2. Site selection and Description of the study area

The Tigray Regional State is located in the northern part of Ethiopia which is subdivided into seven zones including Mekelle - the capital, and 46 administrative Woredas or districts. The study area is located in eastern part of the Regional State of Tigray, Ethiopia. The site of the study area is located in one of the Woredas of the Eastern Tigray Zone administration called Ganta-Afeshum. The topography of the Woreda is characterized by hills and valleys with pick Mountains and valleys and high variation in slope. Like other parts of the region, most of the people living in the Woreda are highly engaged in agriculture, mainly in crop production and animal rearing. The central town of the Woreda is located about 120 KM north of the regional capital Mekelle. The altitude varies from around 1829 meter to 2353 meter in the highlands. The area is highly conducive for honey production and Cactus. The annual average rainfall is between 450 and 500 mm. However, the distribution of the rain is limited to three months (June, July and August) and gets more unreliable in June (CSA, 2008).

Population size of Ganta-Afeshum is, 102765 Out of the total population 48607 are males and 54158 are females. Men headed households are 165558 and 5229 are women headed household among the 21787 of the total households. The total area of the woreda is 59293.09; from this 10800 is cultivated land, 2331.6 irrigated lands, 13996.2 area closure, 1429.7 grazing land and 21675.1 non used lands. The average farm size is 0.5ha per household (WOoARD report, 2018).

The Eastern Zone of the region is crop dependent area with the most fragmented land, which is highly degraded. In addition to the frequent shortage of rainfall, the soil is also less fertile. Consequently, the Eastern zone is among the priority list that deserve intervention by the regional government and other non-governmental organizations.

The map of Tigray regional state, Woredas and study site indicated in figure 2 here below.

Figure 3.1: Map of Tigray Regional State and study area

After prolonged years of civil war, drought and conflicts, Tigray regional state suffered from severe hardship for the last couples of decades. As the result, REST, which is engaged in various development activities in Tigray region initiated and in a move to depart from the more usual direct provision of relief created independent department to supply small credit to rural people called Dedebit Credit and Saving Institution (DECSI). DECSI later grew into a separate institution and was licensed as a microfinance share company in 1997 with the primary mission of improving the wellbeing of those individuals operating in the areas of subsistence agriculture and micro and macro enterprises in the region through increased access to lending and saving services (Dedebit Microfinance, 2011).

DECSI aims to fill the gap of formal institutions by meeting the needs of small scale borrowers in income generating schemes. DECSI delivers multiple types of financial services, namely: credit, saving, money transfer, current account, Gold management, pension payments and TV tax collection in 8 Woredas of 143 functionally decentralized offices (Berhane, 2009). However, DECSI gives priority to rural areas through agricultural credit (constituting 70 percent of DECSI's current loan portfolio) and to women borrowers (Dedebit Microfinance, 2011).

DECSI has target groups that are eligible to get credit such as the poorest of the poor who are

capable of using credit in productive way, people who are dynamic enough to get away from their poverty, micro, small and medium enterprises and women who are in charge of their families (Dedebit Microfinance, 2011). Depending on the type of activity, loan periods range from 1 to 4 years (Nega et al., 2010). This was confirmed by the interview conducted with loan officers. And they noted the maximum loan period for clients in Ganta-Afeshim Woreda is four years and majority of the rural poor people get loan services from DECSI and it is the only micro financial institution in the area. Households can get finance in the Woreda primarily for ox fattening, dairy farming, poultry, Goat and sheep rearing, beehives, solar lighting and water pump..

From the 9 administrative Woredas in Eastern zone, Ganta-Afeshum was purposely targeted for the very reason that the researcher has found it more accessible. Besides, the other Woredas are believed to be similar in their socioeconomic contexts in general and the situation of poor women in particular, in which the result of the study may relatively similar in all the Woredas of the region.

3.3. Research Design

Patton (2011) describes a research design as a structure that is followed in the process of conducting research. It constitutes the blueprint for collection, measurement and analysis of data. Consequently, Francis (2010) defines research design as an organized and systematic way of carrying out research. Thus, this study employed descriptive survey research design. For this reason the researcher used mixed methods, i.e. combination of quantitative and qualitative methods for the assessment of the effect of microfinance on the livelihood of Women. Moreover inferential statistics whereby paired T-test was carried out to compare level of livelihood assets of women clients before and after the microfinance intervention.

Qualitative methods allow researchers to extract feelings, emotions, motivations, perceptions, consumer “language” or self-described behavior. In contrast, quantitative research is a formal systematic approach which incorporates numerical data to obtain information (Cooper, 2011). For this particular research quantitative techniques were used to asses of the effect of microfinance intervention on the target groups. A qualitative method is also used to show the direction of change and individual’s perceptions.

3.4. Target Population

Copper (2011) defines target population as those people, events, or records containing

desired information for the study that determine whether a sample or a census should be selected. Thus the study targeted the 724 women clients of DECSI in five Tabias of Ganta-Afeshum District, in Eastern Tigray, namely Beati – Maymesanu, Bukot –Nehebi, Dibla – Seit, Golah – Genahiti and Sassun –Beithariat. The population encompassed clients who have been engaged in microfinance activities and accessed credit for four years and live in the areas because they are well informed and know much about the pros and cons of microfinance activities, so they can reflect better to this research. These target population were accessed from archive of the institution’s Ganta-Afeshum branch.

3.5. Sampling Procedure, and sample Size

Combinations of purposive, convenient and random sampling methods were employed in this study since the researcher was constrained by resources and time. Purposive method is a non-random sampling method which was used by the researcher to select five Tabias of Ganta-Afeshum district, for the study. The random sampling method was used in contacting the sampled women respondents who were ready and prepared to answer the questionnaire. The sampling procedure facilitated obtaining a sample size of 724 women beneficiaries of DECSI and 5 existing DECSI loan officers working in the selected 5 tabias of Ganta –Afeshum forming 729 persons as a sample frame. First, the loan officers of DECSI were sampled purposively. Purposive sampling is deemed appropriate for selecting officials because it entails identifying individuals who have the required information (Payne & Payne, 2004). Secondly the sampled women based on data provided by DECSI were determined using the Yamane formula (Yamane, 1967).

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where: n = sample size

N = total population of women assisted by the MFI.

e = error term to determine the household sample for the entire women assisted by the MFI in the county using the 95% precision/ confidence level that is appropriate for social research and is chosen because the convenient method reduced the possibility of non-response drastically.

$$n = \frac{724}{1 + 724(0.05 * 0.05)} = 258$$

Hence the sample size in the study therefore was 258 women clients and 5 DECSI loan officers. The number of respondents in each stratified Tabias was decided based on proportionate sampling as shown in the table 1 below.

Table 3.1: the proportionate sample size of women beneficiaries of DECSI in the study area

S.no	Tabia	Women beneficiaries of DECSI	Sample size
1.	Beati – May Mesanu	124	44
2.	Bukot –Nehebi	87	31
3.	Dibla – Seit	224	80
4.	Golah – Genahiti	119	42
5.	Sassun –Beithariat	170	61
	Total	724	258

Source: Dedebit Credit and Saving Institution, Ganta-Afeshum branch, and computed Sample size, 2019

In this regard questionnaires were administered using simple random sampling technique over a period of 3 weeks from 15th April to 5th May, 2019 to the women beneficiaries of DECSI at their various places of businesses and the institution premises while they come to conduct business during the period. This sampling technique was preferred since gives equal opportunity for the target population of the study.

3.6. Source of data and Instruments of data gathering

The study employed both primary and secondary sources of data. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires which were translated to Tigrigna (local language) and semi-structured interview. The Data acquired via interview instrument were used to support and/or cross-check data acquired through the questionnaires.

The secondary data on the other hand were obtained from the annual financial reports of MFIs, data from books, journal articles, proclamation, and government reports in order to explain the effect of microfinance institutions in the livelihood of women in Ganta-Afeshum Woreda.

3.7. Data Reliability and Validity

To enhance the reliability of the data, careful and rigorous design of the questionnaire was made as well as diverse information was collected from different relevant documents, and

several researches were reviewed.

The validity of this research was improved by incorporating only relevant questions in the questionnaires in assessing the issues of interest and helpful to measure what were intended to assess as it were given in the research objectives.

3.8. Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the questionnaires were analyzed by using descriptive analysis such as frequency, percentage, and tables and graphs and inferential statistics such as Paired T-test. SPSS version 20 and MS Excel were used to process the raw data. The Department for International Development (DFID) Sustainable Livelihood Approach was followed for the purpose of data analysis. And thus the analysis included comparison of natural, human, social, physical and financial capital of women before and after loan.

The interview data were subjected to content analysis to describe, decode, translate, and develop understanding through a detailed description of the situation. This analysis allowed distinct comparisons of outcomes and conclusions to be made from the findings

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS OF RESULTS

4.1. Introduction

This Chapter presents the results on the characteristics of respondents and effects of microfinance on the rural livelihood of women. Data were collected through structured questionnaire. Moreover data through interview and secondary data were gathered as supplements to the questionnaire. Out of 258 questionnaires distributed, 234 were duly filled and returned. This marks the response rate of 91%. According to Porter and Umbach (2006), at least (80%) response rate is enough for a descriptive survey study in social science research..

The Chapter has four major sections. The first section describes the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents using descriptive statistics. The second part involves comparison of livelihood assets before and after microfinance intervention using Paired T-test. The third section describes the effect of MFIs on the women's livelihood improvement. The final section presents the challenges facing the women during repayment of loans.

4.2. Demographic and Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

4.2.1. Ages of Respondents

Age is an important social factor that influences individual working ability. Thus, as revealed in table 4.1, out of the total 234 respondents, the majority of the beneficiaries were between the ages of 26-35 forming a total of 45.3 percent. 20.9 percent were between the ages of 16-25 while 29.1 percent were between the ages 36-45. 4.7 percent were above age 45. This indicates that the major age group of women clients of DECSI is predominately middle age. The middle age in the society is the economically active populations who have the potential to engage in farming activities and petty businesses.

The mean age of the respondents was 32 years. The results show that majority of the women are at their younger ages and in the most active and energetic age. This may have an influence on the success and continuity of their small business and thereby contribute to the effect that credit may have in their livelihood.

Table 4.1: Age Distribution of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percent	Mean Age
18-25	49	20.9	32
26-35	106	45.3	
36 -45	68	29.1	
45 and above	11	4.7	
Total	234	100	

SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

4.2.2. Marital Status of Respondents

As revealed in figure 4.1, most of the respondents were married at the time of this study forming 35.5 percent. About 33.3 percent of the respondents were divorced / separated, while those that were widowed formed 16.7 percent followed by 14.5 percent of single women. Divorced/separated and widowed clients together formed 50 percent of the respondents due to more exposure to risks and shocks so that more likely to participation in the DECSI programs. The reason behind could be the fact that divorced/separated households, and widowed clients are less privileged in terms of asset ownership, lack diversified source of income.

Figure 4.1: Marital Status of Respondent

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

4.2.3. Educational Attainments of Respondents

The Educational status of respondents whether skilled or unskilled plays a major role in the success of their businesses. In order to assess the influence of education on access into microfinance services, respondents were asked to state their educational attainment. As shown in figure 4.2, 53.8 percent of women were illiterate whilst 31.2 percent of them had their level of education up to grade eight. 16.2 percent of them had attained education level of high

school and above. This clearly shows that the level of education of most women clients of DECSI is low which is challenging for the women to keep proper records of business, misapplication and appropriation of fund among other things, grasp new techniques and ideas so as to increase their skill. However as revealed in the same table the remaining 46.2 percent of them were educated so that they can grasp new technology and ideas and increases likelihood of participating in the program.

Figure 4.2: Educational Status of Respondent

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

4.2.4. Household Size of Respondents

As clearly shown in table 4.4, the average household size for the sample respondents were four persons and five persons before and after DECSI program respectively ranging from minimum one to maximum eight persons. The higher average household size was reported after DECSI intervention. The average household size of the sampled respondents was substantially higher than the average family size 4.95 at the regional level (CSA, 2012c, p. 13). The average family size prior and after DECSI intervention is about 4.09 and 5.05 respectively. The mean difference in household size were highly statistically significant ($t=7.96$) at 5% significance level. This implies that, the women have more dependents after they participated in the microfinance program and they require higher income to cover all the necessary expenses of the dependents and this can affect the livelihood of the women negatively.

Table 4.2: Household size of respondents

Household Size	Before DECSI intervention		After DECSI intervention	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
1	7	3.0	5	2.1
2	19	8.1	9	3.8
3	49	20.9	18	7.7
4	70	29.9	33	14.1
5	59	25.2	73	31.2
6	21	9.0	67	28.6
7	7	3.0	26	11.1
8	2	0.9	3	1.3
Total	234	100	234	100.0
Mean	4.09		5.05	
t			7.96	
df			233	
Sig. (2-tailed)			0.000	

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

4.2.5. Relationship with the Household Head

As indicated in figure 4.3, the study result shows that majority of the respondents were heads of their households forming 41.5 percent followed by 14.5 percent of spouses of household heads. The remaining 18.4 and 4.7 percent of them had daughter and sister relationship with their respective household heads respectively.

Therefore it can be understood from this result that most of women clients Of DECSI were heads of their households. This might be due to more participation divorced/separated and widowed women than others in the DECSI program as mentioned in figure 4.1 above and generally in Tigray, females become heads only if either they are divorced, separated or widowed.

Figure 4.3: The relationship of the respondents with the head of the household

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

4.2.6. Main Economic Activity

Agriculture remains the dominant sector in terms of its contribution to livelihood, income and employment in the majority of the developing countries. Households in rural areas obtain more than half of their income from farming. The study equally sought to find out the main business activities that respondents are engaged in and whether loans are invested into their existing businesses.

As seen in table 4.6, the main economic activity in which most of the respondents engaged was farming making up 62.8% while the remaining 37.2 percent of them run micro business for their livelihood. This result can indicate that due to the rural area they reside, the main occupation of the respondents was farming and engaged in microenterprise activity as a source of income diversification. This calls for MFI intervention in which generally DECSI loan scheme in rural area is primarily intended for farming activities. In line with this IFAD (2001) noted that in the absence of non-farm income generating activities, agriculture remains the primary occupation for most households.

Figure 4.4: Major economic activity of the respondents

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

4.2.7. Total land holding size

Land is the basic asset and source of livelihood for the rural community. And land holding size is a critical factor for sustainable livelihood and asset accumulation in rural areas. As clearly seen in table 4.3 below, the land distribution among the rural household vary from household to household. Consequently, in the study area the average land holdings per household before and after DECSI intervention were 0.475 ha (1.9 tsimad) and 0.478 ha (1.91 tsimad) respectively. Out of the total land holdings, average of the cultivated land per household prior and after DECSI intervention were 0.377 ha (1.51 tsimad) and 0.38 ha (1.52 tsimad) respectively. The result shows that there is statistically a significant at 5% with P values of $P < 0.05$. This slight change of land size after DECSI intervention was due to twfriti³. However, it is more below the national average land size, which is 1.02 ha and Tigray region average 0.54 ha (Menberu, 2014).

Table 4.3: Total Holding and Cultivated Land Size of the households

Land size	Before DECSI intervention				After DECSI intervention			
	Total holding		cultivated		Total holding		cultivated	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
0.25 1 (tsimad)	-	-	41	17.5			39	16.7
0.31 ha 1.25(tsimad)	35	15.0	33	14.1	32	13.7	31	13.2
0.38 ha 1.5(tsimad)	27	11.5	60	25.6	25	10.7	61	26.1
0.44 ha .75(tsimad)	56	23.9	52	22.2	58	24.8	54	23.1
0.50 ha 2(tsimad)	41	17.5	35	15.0	43	18.4	36	15.4
0.63 ha 2.5(tsimad)	62	26.5	-	-	63	26.9		
Total	221	94.4	221	94.4	221	94.4	221	94.4
Lack of Land	13	5.6	13	5.6	13	5.6	13	5.6
Total	234	100	234	100	234	100	234	100
Mean	0.475 ha		0.377 ha		0.478 ha		0.380 ha	
	t			Sig. (2-tailed)				
Land Holding Size	3.44			.001				
Cultivated land	3.23			.001				

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

4.3. Credit and Saving History of respondents

According to the interview conducted with loan officers in sampled tabias, the loan products of the DECSI are designed in such a way to create new income and employment activities in poor communities whose livelihood is dependent on agriculture, contribute to the improvement of living standards and increase the overall prosperity of these communities.

³ 'Tiwfirti' is an agreement to give a plot of land to other to plough the land on the bases of sharecropping and straw

Currently DECSI Loan in the study area covers cattle, goat, sheep, poultry, beehive, solar light and water pump.

As clearly seen in table 4.4, most of the respondents forming 73.1 percent joined the MFI to access credit facilities while the remaining 23.9 percent joined the MFI for both credit and saving purposes. Concerning loan requirements, majority of respondents consisting of 81.6 percent took individual loans and replied that they had to use personal guarantor as the main collateral. However the remaining 18.8 percent of them took group loans since they have used social collateral (group joint guarantee) as a security. This shows that individual loan borrowers are greater than group loan clients. This in turn shows the convenience and preference of individual loan over group loan that make loan repayment jointly liable.

With regard to duration of membership in DECSI program, most of respondents constituting 50.9 percent had business to do with the MFI for more than 10 years followed by 39.3.9 percent that have been with the MFI for 8 to 10 years. At the same time 9.8 percent of them have been members in DECSI program for 5 to 7 years. Moreover majority of respondents forming 45.3 percent followed by 37.6 percent of them took loans seven and five respectively. It can be concluded from this result, most of the women clients retained due to the fact that the MFI created mutual trust with its clients and brought services in their door steps easily using personal guarantor method.

Concerning the purpose of the credit, most of respondents comprising of 52.6 percent intended for the acquisition of livestock and agricultural inputs. However 27.8 percent and 19.7 percent of them aimed to use the loan as housekeeping money and starting business respectively, though DECSI under normal circumstances does not encourage the delivery of credit for consumption purposes. Thus long duration clients' membership, repeat loans and amount of loan taken can influence the effect of the microfinance services thereby contribute to the livelihood improvement of the women.

Table 4.4: Credit and Saving History of respondents

Item		Frequency	Percent
Purpose of joining the DECSI	Savings	-	-
	Credit	171	73.1
	Both	63	26.9
	Total	234	100.0
Loan Requirements	Personal guarantor	191	81.6
	Social collateral	43	18.4
	Saving	-	-
	Total	234	100.0
Duration of Membership in DECSI program	5-7 years	23	9.8
	8-10 years	92	39.3
	above 10 years	119	50.9
	Total	234	100.0
Number of times loan taken	Amount of cumulative loan (birr)		
5	75,000 - 95,000	21	9.0
6	100,000 - 120,000	88	37.6
7	125,000 - 130,000	106	45.3
8	135,000 - 140,000	19	8.1
	Total	234	100.0
Type of loan accessed from DECSI program	Individual loan	191	81.6
	Group loan	43	18.4
	Total	234	100.0
Lloan disbursement	Purchasing livestock for breeding and agricultural inputs	123	52.6
	Serving as housekeeping money	65	27.8
	Starting business	46	19.7
	Total	234	100.0

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

4.4. Status of Livelihood Assets before and after joining DECSI

This section presents findings of women clients' livelihood capital situation before and after participating in DECSI credit program based on the DFID livelihood framework (1991), which identifies five capital assets – natural, physical financial, human and social, from which individuals construct their livelihood.

4.4.1. Natural Capital

The livelihood of people living in developing countries especially in rural areas is strongly depending on the natural resources base (land, forest, water...), known as natural capital in the SLA (Solesbury, 2003).

Ownership of irrigated land has also assumed to have positive effect on the probability of

borrowing as it is mainly used to produce cash crops. As indicated in table 4.5 the total area of the irrigated land of the sample respondents was slightly increased from 0.09 ha (0.38 tsimad) to 0.1 ha (0.39 tsimad) after joining DECSI as statistically significant using t-statistics ($t=2.58$)

Table 4.5: Irrigated land of respondents prior and after joining DECSI

Does the household own irrigated land?			before joining DECSI		after joining DECSI	
			Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Yes	0.06 ha (0.25 tsimad)		22	9.4	19	8.1
	0.08 ha (0.33 tsimad)		37	15.8	36	15.4
	0.13 ha (0.5 tsimad)		38	16.2	42	17.9
	Total		97	41.5	97	41.5
No		137	58.5	137	58.5	
Total		234	100.0	234	100.0	
Mean			0.09 ha (0.38 tsimad)		0.1 ha (0.39 tsimad)	
t			2.58			
df			96			
Sig. (2-tailed)			0.011			

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

Respondents were asked whether they acquired more land through rent, lease or investment prior and after joining DECSI credit program. However as depicted in table 4.6 below they rated the possibility of acquiring additional land through rent, lease or investment as low (mean= 1.97) since, land is neither bought nor sold. This was also confirmed through statistically insignificant ($t= 0.22$) difference in mean scores before and after joining DECSI intervention,

The supply and provision of water and improved sanitation services is an important means to achieve sustainable households' livelihood. Thus respondents were asked to rate improvement of water and sanitation availability. Accordingly the respondents rated the availability of water and sanitation facility after DECSI intervention as high since the households become the owners of self-dug water wells, pit latrines and hand wash through gained income. The results of the findings also revealed statistically significant increase in the mean scores of improved provision of water ($t= 12.61$) and sanitation facility ($t= 13.95$) respectively after DECSI intervention. Thus it is possible to conclude that DECSI credit program contributed to improving livelihoods for rural women due to safe sanitation and minimizing unnecessarily travel of long distance to fetch water.

Table 4.6: Sustainable status of the natural capitals for sample women clients

Natural capitals	Before the intervention		After the intervention		t	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev		
land acquisition through rent, lease or investment	1.94	.834	1.97	.814	0.46	.646
water availability from spring water/ hand-dug well	3.04	.84	3.96	.87	12.61	.000
Soil conservation	3.03	.85	3.94	.85	11.41	.000
Availability of sanitation and hygiene facilities such as a latrine, hand washing,	2.95	.83	3.950	.87	13.95	.000

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

Considering five point liket scale (1) very low, (2) Low, (3) medium, (4) high, (5) very high, mean average values were interpreted as 0.05-1.50 very low, 1.51-2.50 low, 2.51 – 3.50 = medium, 3.51 – 4.50 = high and above 4.50 very high.

Crop and livestock production are the major agricultural practices in the study area. Nearly 90 percent of the respondents reported that they involve in either crop production, livestock husbandry, or both. The objective of crop cultivation is mainly for home consumption with negligible amount of output devoted for marketing. The main cereal crops produced include wheat, barley, hanfets⁴, teff, maize/corn, horse beans/field peas, and lentil.

The households in the study area prioritize food security by devoting considerable amount of their produce for home consumption. And only during an increase in yield, the households are expected to market crop products over food consumption requirement to meet their cash demands. Due to low irrigation land, there are low practices of vegetable and fruit productions and commonly potatoes, carrots, garlic, onions and cabbage grew in the study area.

As depicted in table 4.7, statistically a significant difference in average yield of cereal crops and vegetables harvest prior and after DECSI credit scheme. The increase of crops and vegetables / fruits output might be due to use of fertilizer, improved seeds and pesticide usage. In line with this Zeller & Sharma (2000) indicated that credit enables smallholder farmers to invest in land improvements, and thereby to adopt new agricultural technologies such as high-yielding seeds and fertilizers that increase their efficiency and income. However

⁴ hanfets is wheat and barley are often intercropped, in a mixture.

according to the interview with the loan officers, DECSI credit program mainly intended for livestock and its products, poultry and beehives in the study area. The exclusion of loan for crops was due to limited production that only fulfills their food requirements.

Table 4.7: Crops and vegetables harvest (in quintal) of respondents prior and after the DECSI intervention

Crops and vegetables harvest	N	Before the DECSI intervention		After the DECSI intervention		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev			
Wheat	210	4.652	0.531	6.066	1.456	13.12	219	.000
Barely	211	4.600	0.530	5.953	1.376	13.02	210	.000
Hanfets	73	4.527	0.506	6.178	1.492	9.12	72	.000
Teff	56	4.406	0.492	6.223	1.470	8.67	55	.000
Maize	77	4.623	0.494	5.786	1.413	6.91	76	.000
Horse beans	35	4.586	0.503	5.936	1.253	6.26	34	.000
Lentil	30	4.500	0.509	5.983	1.545	4.71	29	.000
Potatoes	96	2.469	0.502	3.458	0.501	14.41	95	.000
Carrot	95	2.542	0.509	3.521	0.510	14.28	94	.000
Onion	93	2.513	0.501	3.481	0.506	12.53	92	.000
Cabbages	94	2.391	0.494	3.444	0.503	16.22	93	.000

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

4.4.2. Physical capital

Livestock contributes directly or indirectly to the livelihood of rural households as food consumption and income generation (Jazen and Carter, 2013). DECSI credit program also mainly intended for livestock and its products, poultry and beehives. During the survey, as depicted in table 4.8 the respondents have reported similar high increase in the number of livestock ownership after accessing DECSI credit. However, the difference of goat ($t=10.8$) and hen ($t=9.9$) is relatively higher than cattle ($t=6.66$). Thus the productivity of small ruminants namely goat/sheep and poultry were very encouraging.

In contrast, in the case of horse, donkey and bee ownership, the respondents reported that there was no difference before and after joining DECSI. Generally donkey is not included in DECSI credit program in the study area. Accordingly the average numbers of livestock holding of the survey sample in TLU was 1.45 TLU and 1.87 TLU before and after accessing DECSI credit scheme respectively. Thus it is possible to conclude that the effect of DECSI's credit scheme on the livestock ownership of its clients is statistically significant as it has reported improvements in majority of livestock ownership or sustained the existing livestock.

Table 4.8: Type and Mean number of Livestock Ownership of respondents before after joining DECSI

Livestock/ poultry	Before joining DECSI				After joining DECSI				t	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	N	Sum	Mean	TLU	N	Sum	Mean	TLU			
Cattle	123	233	1.89	233	123	307	2.5	307	6.66	0.00	
Goat/sheep	119	467	3.92	60.71	124	611	4.93	79.43	10.8	0.00	
Donkey	46	45	0.98	31.5	41	51	1.24	35.7	2.2	.037	
Horse	16	18	0.8	13.5	14	18	1	14.25	1.0	0.34	
Hen	99	242	2.44	3.15	92	341	3.71	4.43	9.9	0.00	
Total TLU ⁵				341.9					440.8		
Mean TLU				1.46					1.88		
Bee	27	26	0.96		23	24	1.04		0.33	0.75	

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

Figure 4.5: Sheep breeding after accessing credit

Figure 4.6: Fattening of Holstein Ox

⁵ TLU=> Cattle=1.00, horse = 0.75, donkey =0.7, goat/sheep=0.13, poultry =0.013 Source: Storck, *et at.*, (1991)

Figure 4.7: Poultry production in tabia Bukot-Nehbi

Figure 4.8: Beekeeping in a Gola-Genahiti

Table 4.9: Physical capital- household furniture and agricultural equipment before and after joining DECSI credit scheme

Household furniture and agricultural equipment	Before joining DECSI			After joining DECSI			t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	N	Sum	Mean	N	Sum	Mean			
Radio/tape recorder	213	209	.98	213	214	1.00	2.26	212	.025
Bed	46	45	.98	46	50	1.09	2.34	45	.024
Chair	41	45	1.10	38	45	1.18	1.36	37	.183
Mobile phone	80	134	1.68	80	141	1.76	2.75	79	.007
Barrel	167	164	.98	167	170	1.02	2.49	166	.014
Kettle	215	210	.98	215	219	1.02	2.76	214	.006
Cooking Stoves	33	23	.70	33	33	1.00	3.73	32	.001
Plowing Set	232	234	1.01	232	237	1.02	1.74	231	.083
Axe	206	203	.99	206	206	1.00	0.77	205	.440
Sickle	233	446	1.91	233	460	1.97	3.04	232	.003
Spade	221	219	.99	221	221	1.00	1.42	220	.158
wheelbarrow	51	47	.92	51	51	1.00	2.06	50	.044
Hammer	204	196	.96	204	204	1.00	2.26	212	.025
Water pump	92	58	.63	91	91	1.00	2.34	45	.024

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

The survey investigated the livelihood situations in household commodities of sampled women after joining the DECSI credit scheme. And as revealed in the table 4.9, there is some change in possession of the furniture and agricultural equipment of the sample respondents except for chair, axe, and spade.

The results showed statistically slight changes on household items including radio/tape

recorder, bed, mobile phone, barrel, kettle, cooking stoves, plowing set, sickle, wheelbarrow , hammer and water pump which are owned by almost all the sample respondents found to be significant at 5% with P values of $P < 0.05$. However, the change that they have achieved is not yet satisfactory.

4.4.3. Financial capital

Data on household income is a useful indicator of the socio-economic status of households. During the survey the sample respondents were requested to indicate their economic status before and after joining DECSI. Table 4.10 shows that average income from farming from farming has significantly increased from birr 6,504.12 (prior to credit) to birr 8,210.88 (after to credit which is an increase of 26 percent. Similarly average income from off-farming prior and after credit was birr 5,451.36 and 7,926.48 respectively with a increase of birr 2,475.12 (45 percent).

In addition diversification of income sources to non-farm microenterprises is a common livelihood strategy in rural areas. Accordingly 31.2 percent, 24.8 percent, 19.2 percent and 13.7 percent of respondents saw a significant difference in their income of house, land or agricultural rent, local drink sale, kiosks and artisan product sales respectively after joining DECSI. Statistically the results found to be significant at 5% with p value of $p = 0.000$. It can be understand from the result the respondents got more income from sales of livestock and crop products. This is due to the fact that the majority of rural dwellers depend on crop production and livestock rearing to support their livelihood. This implies that the loans have made it possible for the respondents to acquire more financial assets.

Thus access to micro finance services help the women to have more sources of finance, which in turn allows them to purchase improved agricultural inputs, and help them to improve their farming management. The resulting data on income has revealed a statistically significant increase from what has been prior DECSCI credit access across all the sources of income. In line with this, Asmelash (2003) said that after accessing credit rural households can improve their agricultural productions and diversify their income from agricultural and non-agricultural activities.

Table 4.10: Average farming and off- farming incomes of respondents per year before and after joining DECSI credit scheme (in birr)

Farm and non farm incomes	N	%	Before joining DECSI		After joining DECSI		t	Sig. (2-tailed)
			Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.		
Farming								
Livestock products sale	224	95.7	2,831.76	63.46	3,677.16	74.68	27.6	.000
Cereals and fruits product sale income	224	95.7	3,672.36	74.36	4,533.72	37.37	28.7	.000
Total			6,504.12		8,210.88			
Non-Farming								
Incomes from small shops/kiosks	45	19.2	1,440.00	24.77	2,160.00	65.54	9.4	.000
Local drink sale	58	24.8	1,440.00	24.49	2,153.76	64.93	10.6	.000
Artisan products sale	32	13.7	1,136.28	25.4	1,462.56	25.20	17.3	.000
Rental income from house, land, or agricultural equipment	73	31.2	1,435.08	24.75	2,150.16	65.19	12.0	.000
Total			5,451.36		7,926.48			

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

4.4.4. Human capital

The survey addressed human capital of sample respondents particularly their investment on health and education prior and after accessing DECSI credit scheme.

As revealed in table 4.11, majority of respondents forming of 98.3 and 98 percent showed agreement for the significant improvement in their ability to send the member or family for education and get update information respectively after joining DECSI. Moreover majority of the respondents consisting of both 97.9 percent agreed that they have improved their financial and livestock management skill respectively.

With regard to health, majority of the respondents comprising 99.1 percent agreed that enjoyed improvement in their health. However 95.3 percent of respondents averagely agreed (mean=2.48) for getting change being a beneficiary of the community Based Health Insurance. Statistically the results found to be highly significant at 5% with p value $P < 0.05$. This clearly indicate that there was a change for better skill and health status of families after microfinance intervention and hence improvement in their general livelihood.

Table 4.11:: Human capital of respondents relating to education and health before and after joining DECSI credit scheme

Item Description	%	Before	After Joining	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Joining DECSI	DECSI		
		Mean	Mean		
able to join school, college or University	98.3	2.53	3.52	161.57	.000
listen to radio to get update information	98.0	2.48	3.49	118.00	.000
enjoying good health to develop capacity to work	99.1	2.56	3.56	115.75	.000
beneficiary of the community Based Health Insurance	95.3	1.48	2.48	156.62	.000
have financial skill to manage your business	97.9	2.49	3.49	230.00	.000
have livestock management skill	97.9	2.48	3.48	228.00	.000

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

4.4.5. Social Capital

Literature has identified social capital and trust as key assets for the poor in recovery from stresses and shocks and in accumulating assets (Woolcock 2001).

As revealed in table 4.12, majority of the respondents reported high participation in women farmer association, community activity and governance and Idir⁶, Equip⁷ and Mahber⁸ membership after accessing DECSI credit scheme. However the women's Participation in religious association and in the meetings of governmental and NGO programs or in other social events after taking loan was still low as prior to credit access. Hence it can be deduced from the results that the women improved their social capital after accessing DECSI scheme as the differences in the rating of their participation status is statistically significant. In line with this Fong and Perrett (1991) pointed out that the direct provision of micro credit to women is one of several ways to initiate a process of social and economic change for women.

⁶ Edir - is a traditional community organization whose members assist each other during the mourning process

⁷ Equip - is a traditional way of saving money where by members contribute some and equal amount of money and take the amount on lottery method.

⁸ Mahiber is established to fulfill spiritual commitments of individuals usually named after Saints.

Table 4.12: Rating of social capital of women before and after DECSI

Participation status	N	%	Before	After	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
			Mean	Mean			
Participation in Women farmer association	215	91.9	2.51	3.50	20.08	214	.000
Participation in community activity and governance	229	97.9	2.53	3.51	20.5	228	.000
Participation in Idir, Equip and mahber membership	223	95.3	2.49	3.48	21.03	222	.000
Participation in Religious association	230	98.3	1.53	2.06	8.77	229	.000
Participation in the meetings of governmental and NGO programs or in other social events	195	83.3	1.48	2.01	7.40	194	.000

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

Figure 4.9: Women participating in a meeting in Tabia Sasun in ARD office

4.5. Women’s participation in household decision

The respondents in the male headed household were asked to rate their participation status in household decision. Accordingly, as depicted in table 4.13 all respondents took part in household decision making in aspects of modification or repair of house, in issues of their children education and marriage of their sons/daughters before joining the DECSI and made a significant increase in participation after accessing the DECSI credit.

Similarly 98.5 percent of respondent participated in household decision before accessing credit in aspects of livestock purchase/ sale and their family member illness followed by 97.8 percent of them in aspects of family planning with a significant positive change after getting loan. The results show high participation of rural women in the in issues of children education, family medication and marriage of their sons/daughters. This indicates that the

respondents felt that microfinance credit enhanced their involvement in major male headed household decisions. In contrast there was still lowly taking part of the sample respondents in house repairs, livestock acquisition or sale and family planning after accessing credit. The reason of significant limit for women not to participate in these aspects may be due to the power deeply rooted in our social systems and values and it is tilted towards men and gender relation.

Table 4.13:: Women’s participation in household decision in male headed households

Women’s participation	N	%	Before joining DECSI		After joining DECSI		t	Sig. (2-tailed)
			Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.		
Participation in aspects of modification or repair of house	136	100	2.41	.49	2.84	.76	6.94	.000
Participation in purchase or sale of livestock	134	98.5	2.45	.50	2.83	.75	6.47	.000
Participation in issues of children education	136	100	2.68	.47	3.06	.64	6.57	.000
Participation in aspects of their family member illness	134	98.5	3.33	.65	3.4	.54	2.40	.018
Participation in aspects of family planning	133	97.8	2.56	.5	2.95	.61	6.12	.000
Participation in marriage of son/daughter	136	100	2.88	.63	3.08	.61	4.51	.000

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

4.6. Women Household Livelihood Improvement

The study had as one of its objectives to identify the effect of the microfinance on the living conditions of the beneficiaries. This was done by asking respondents to assess their living conditions before and after they accessed the loans. This aspect of the study looked at the effect micro finance on the livelihood of the respondents.

The researcher wanted to know the effect of microfinance on the properties of the respondents and the respondents were asked whether microfinance institutions had improved their asset or not. As the results in table 4.14 demonstrates, 98.3 percent of the respondents confirmed that they had a positive observation view towards microfinance getting some form of improvements to their prosperities after loan, while a small proportion (1.7 percent) said even though they have received the loans but they have not made any improvement changes

to their properties following credit access.

With the proportion the women clients saw positive impact in their business, 50 percent increased purchase of agricultural product followed by renovation of house comprising of 23.1 percent. The remaining 14.1 percent and 7.7 percent of them used their loan to construct additional rooms and build kiosks respectively.

Thus, it can be deduced that, the DECSI credit scheme had made improvement in the properties of the sample women household. This confirms a study by Littlefield et al, (2003)(which said that, the micro-credit programs offered to rural women have created significant positive differences in their businesses.

The clients were also asked whether they felt that their income improved after being members of DECSI. As a result, most of them (78.2 percent) agreed that their income had improved while a small proportion (21.8 percent) felt that there was no change in their income.

Table 4.14: Improvement made in the properties and performance of income of the respondents after accessing DECSI credit program

Item		Frequency	Percent	
Is three recent improvements to the property (ies) after the association with the DECSI?	Yes	Improvements made		
		Constructed Rooms	33	14.1
		Built kiosk	18	7.7
		Increased purchase of inputs	118	50.4
		Renovate building	61	26.1
	Total	230	98.3	
	No	4	1.7	
Total	234	100		
Is there Improvement in the performance of your income since joining the DECSI?	Yes	183	78.2	
	No	51	21.8	
	Total	234	100.0	

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

The income flow of the households can affect the economic benefit of the borrowers and the possibility to secure a loan repayment without compromising the future of the poor households. Thus the study also sought to find out the change of average annual income of the respondents before and after accessing the DECSI credit scheme. As table 4.15 depicts, in order to see the yearly income revenue of the respondents the researcher used to categorize in to five scales with the variance of 3000 Birr.

When a comparative analysis was made between the income of the respondents before and after the credit, 2.6 percent of them had their annual income below birr 6000 before getting loan. However after accessing credit, the respondents with yearly income below birr 6000 were slightly decreased to 0.9 percent. Similarly there was an increase to those whose annual income was above birr 15,000 from 11.5 percent before joining DECSI to 67.1 percent after accessing credit.

After running a paired t test, there was a significant average difference of the annual income after and before accessing credit ($t = 29.26, p < 0.00$). On average, annual income of the respondents after credit was birr 1,661.56 higher than the annual income before credit access. It can be deduced from this result, accessing the DECSI credit scheme has positive effect on the income of the women clients. This supports what Navajas et. al., (2000) assumed that, micro finance equally increases household income, improves the consumption patterns and lifestyles of the rural families. The positive impact on income has increased their asset position and has created wealth for the family (Hulme and Mosely, 2003).

Table 4.15: Annual Income of respondents before and after Accessing DECSI credit

Annual income (birr)	before joining the DECSI		after joining the DECSI		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent			
<6,000	6	2.6	2	0.9	29.26	233	0.00
6,000 - 9,000	41	17.5	13	5.6			
9,001-12,000	51	21.8	18	7.7			
12,001-15,000	109	46.6	44	18.8			
> 15,000	27	11.5	157	67.1			
Total	234	100	234	100			
Mean	12,123.18		14,846.15				
Std. Dev.	2,858.41		2,691.5				

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

The study assessed the effect the MFI credit scheme has had on the social recognition (i.e. how the society regard the beneficiary women, in terms of status, respect and involvement in decision making etc) of the women.

It is clear that upon the improvement of the social recognition that people especially women be part of decision making at the household and community level as well. Before accessing the loan, 91.9 percent of the respondents said that they were consulted in making household decisions. But after the loan, the percentage has increased to 96.2 percent. It can be deduced from this result that the women's social recognition was very good and after access of credit

their involvement in household decisions got a significant increment of 4.3 percent which is encouraging.

Table 4.16: Consulted in making household decisions before and after joining the DECSI

Item		Before joining DECSI		After joining DECSI	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Consulted in making household decisions	Yes	215	91.9	225	96.2
	No	19	8.1	9	3.8
	Total	231	98.7	232	99.1
Mean		0.96		1.0	
				3.23	
Sig. (2-tailed)				0.001	

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

People's ability to escape poverty depends on the achieving of sustainable livelihoods through access to a range of livelihood resources (natural, economic, human, social and physical capital) which are combined in the pursuit of different livelihood strategies (Scoones, 1998).

As revealed in table 4.18 below, majority of respondents consisting of 98.7 percent and 98.3 percent as indicated in tables 4.14 confirmed that they saw improvements in their livelihood assets and got progress in their livelihood outcome respectively after accessing the credit. It can be concluded from the results that, there have been some significant changes in livelihood capitals and in the living conditions of the respondents after accessing the loan.

Table 4.17: Improvement in the livelihood assets and wellbeing of women since joining the DECSI

Item		Frequency	Percent
Improvement of asset	Yes	231	98.7
	No	3	1.3
	Total	234	100.0
Improvement of wellbeing	Yes	230	98.3
	No	4	1.7
	Total	234	100.0

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

4.7. Challenges during Loan Repayment

The researcher wanted to know the perceptions of clients on loan interest rates charged by the DECSI. Interest rate charged for a loan has effects on the amount of profit that the borrowers are expected to gain as well on the repayment of loan amount.

As revealed in table majority of respondents forming of 56 percent evaluated the loan interest rates charged as high followed by 44 percent as fair. This indicated that most respondents were sensitive to interest rate charged as 'high price sensitivity'. The 17 percent interest rate is actually higher than the rate charged by formal banks which ranges from 9.5-15 percent per annum. This implies that the interest rate may be affordable for small enterprises owners who found it difficult to access loans from banks; however it was not affordable for the poorest households who found it difficult to access loans from both the microfinance and banks. The results goes to confirm Murdoch's (1999:1574) work which indicated that, one of the challenges that the poor faced is that, microfinance has high interest rates.

With regard to repayment for the loan, majority of respondents forming of 53.8 percent weighed up loan period as quite short unlike 43.2 percent who viewed loan period as quite enough. However majority of respondents comprising of 75.2 percent confirmed for paying on the schedule. This might be fear of loan interest increase and lose of access to subsequent loans.

Table 4.18: Views of respondents towards loan repayment

Item			Frequency	Percent	
Interest rate charged for the loan			High	131	56
			Fair	103	44
			Total	234	100
Repayment period for the loan?			Quite short	126	53.2
			Quite enough	108	46.8
			Total	234	100
Ability of repayment of the loan on schedule?	Yes	Extent of loan repayment so far	Great	73	31.2
			Moderate	103	44.0
			Total	176	75.2
	No	extent of challenges faced while repaying the loan	Great	41	17.5
			Moderate	17	7.3
			Total	58	24.8
Total			234	1000	

Source: SPSS Output from Survey Data, 2019

A further question was also asked to those who didn't pay their loan on time to find challenges facing the clients during loan repayment. It was identified that a high rate of interest and lack of access to credit which is associated with inability to meet down payment requirements were their major challenge. There were also complaints about group lending as it makes them jointly liable. Other challenge identified was loan period not sufficient enough for attaining a full cost recovery particularly with the increasing inflation rate in the country. Failure of crops, death of livestock, drought and other natural calamity were identified for delay of repayment. If the loan does not repay on time, interest rate increases from time to time, then borrowers are more in risk. The women indicated that, they always had to work under pressure or use their own capital to repay the loan. This was also confirmed through interview conducted with loan officers that spending of loan on non-intended purposes and not to pay on due time.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Introduction

This Chapter presents the summary, conclusion, and recommendations drawn from the study. Descriptive and inferential methods using T-paired test were used to analyze the data set in view of the research problem and objectives set out at the beginning of the thesis. The findings prove that women households who were clients of the DECSI has shown statistically significantly higher values in the livelihood outcome after accessing DECSI credit scheme as compared with prior to DECSI intervention. This chapter has three sections. The first section summarizes the main descriptive findings. The second section draws the conclusion of the study. And the last section outlines recommendations and suggests for future research.

5.2. Summary

The study was sought to assess the effect of microfinance on the livelihood of women a case of Dedebit Credit and Savings Institution in Ganta-Afeshum district, Eastern Tigray. In particular, the study provides answers to the following three main research questions: (1) does microfinance contribute to improving the livelihood and well-being of the women or otherwise, (2) what effect does access to microfinance has on raising the women's participation in household decision, and (3) what are the challenges faced by the women in repayment of loans from the microfinance.

Assessing the effect of microfinance programs in terms of whether it is improving the livelihood of the targeted population or not has a vital significance to the concerned authorities so that an appropriate policy intervention and correct choices would be made that delivers maximum benefits.

Ganta-Afeshum woreda is one among 34 woredas in Eastern zone of the Tigray predominantly dependent on agriculture for their livelihood, employment and income. Poverty is largely concentrated in rural areas and disproportionately affects women.

Due to low economic activity and poverty in rural areas, the formal banks are not extending finance to the rural people. DECSI aims to fill the gap of formal institutions by meeting the needs of small scale borrowers in income generating schemes. As reviewed in the literature that there are multidimensional channels through which microfinance can positively affects

rural livelihood and reduce poverty. However, it is tend to be inconclusive whether DECSI's intervention is leading to success.

The study adopted a conceptual approach called the Sustainable Livelihood Approach (SLA) which focuses on household client having a set physical, human, natural, financial, and social assets so that to achieve specific livelihood outcomes (consumption, asset possession, food security, savings, manage risks and shocks, etc.). With this approach, the effect of micro financial resources to the women household livelihood was assessed.

During the study a total 258 women DECSI clients and 5 DECSI loan officers were selected using combinations of convenient, purposive and random sampling methods. The survey data were collected through structured questionnaire from the clients and semi structured interview with the loan officers. Descriptive statistics were computed to describe the main features of the data. Accordingly, the mean age of the total sample was 33 years. The results show that majority of the women are at their younger ages and in the most active and energetic age. Majority of respondents (73.1 percent) accessed individual loan DECSI for the purpose of purchasing livestock and agricultural inputs (52.6 percent)) using personal guarantor (81.6 percent) as security.

The first objective of the study was to analyze the contributions of DECSI to improving or otherwise the livelihoods and wellbeing of women. The findings show that land and livestock ownership was common among the sample respondents. The average land holdings per household prior DECSI intervention (0.475 ha) shows a slight change after the intervention (0.478 ha) due to twftri. The effect of DECSI's credit scheme on the livestock ownership of its clients is statistically significant as it has reported improvements in majority of livestock ownership.

Respondents grew primarily cereal crops as well as vegetable and fruit which were small as compared to cereal harvest mainly for consumption purposes. The significant difference was observed in the average cereal, vegetable and fruit yield production before and after DECSI credit scheme. However according to the interview with the loan officers, since such output difference is not stable due frequent exposure to shocks/stress, drought, and cost of living etc.), and market related problems the crops.

The sample respondents own the basic household furniture and agricultural inputs and there is slight change in their possession after accessing loan except for chair, axe, and spade. However the change that they have achieved was not yet satisfactory.

Households in rural areas engage not only in farm activities (63 percent) but also in nonfarm microenterprises for consumption, income generation or risk alleviation purposes. The livelihood outcome as measured by average annual income, average livestock, and house furniture and agricultural equipments was found statistically significantly higher after accessing DECSI credit than prior to joining the DECSI. On average, annual income of the respondents after credit (birr 14,846.15) was birr 1,661.56 higher than the annual income before credit access (birr 12,123.18). Thus The sampled women households has made improvement in the properties namely increased purchase of agricultural inputs (50.4 percent), renovation of their house (26.1) and construction of rooms (14.1) and Building of kiosks (7.7 percent) after accessing DECSI credit scheme.

Majority of respondents agreed for enjoying improvement in their family education (98.3 percent) and in their health status of their families (99.1 percent) after joining DECSI credit scheme. Similarly the findings show high participation of sample women in women farmer association, community activity and governance and Idir, Equip and Mahber membership after accessing DECSI credit scheme.

The second objective of the study was to examine the effect of DECSI on raising the women's participation in household decision-making. At most all (more than 97 percent) of sampled women took part in household decision making in the male headed household in aspects of modification or repair of house, in issues of their children education and marriage of their sons/daughters, livestock acquisition or sale and family health and family planning before joining the DECSI and made a significant increase in participation after accessing the DECSI credit. The results show high participation of rural women in issues of children education, family medication and marriage of their sons/daughters. The respondents felt that microfinance credit enhanced their involvement in major household decisions. In contrast there was still lowly taking part of the sample respondents in house repairs, livestock acquisition or sale and family planning after accessing credit.

The final objective of the study was to identify the challenges faced by the women in repayments of loans borrowed from the microfinance. Majority of the respondents complained that the high interest rate, short loan period, drought and other calamity were challenging them and causing repayment default.

5.3. CONCLUSION

Based on the major findings, the following conclusions were drawn. The study concludes that the DECSI has significant effect on the livelihood of women households in rural areas in Ganta-Afeshum Woreda, Tigray.

The researcher found out from the respondents whether after accessing the loans there have been an increased livelihood outcomes or otherwise (that is increased outcome, reduced vulnerability and improved food security or not).

The client households might use the borrowed funds in a multiple ways that best serve their interest and fill their financing gap. Given the fact that the livelihoods of the sampled households are mainly dependent on agriculture, the decision to engage in off-farm microenterprises was an attempt to diversify their income sources and ensure livelihood stability. The values of assets particularly livestock and cereal crops were found to be significantly higher implying DECSI could have enabled either to add new ones or sustain the existing livestock by purchasing forage for feed and used fertilizers, improved seeds or pesticides for crops.

The findings of the study revealed that, provision of financial services to the poor women improved access to education and medical facilities and developed better financial skill to manage their business. The survey results showed the participation of women in community activity and governance, social and religious associations and events as well women farmer association was high. In this regard DECSI's microfinancing scheme has a positive effect improving of the women household capital.

Due to building of social and human capital and, financial capital through social intermediaries offered by the microfinance, the sample women household in male headed household increased their livelihood in terms of improved decision-making role in their community and household.

However, the study revealed that women farmers faced various constraints such as high interest rates, short loan period and lack of access to credit due to inability to repay the previous loan

Overall, the findings confirmed that the provision of micro financial resources enabled the rural women to improve their rural livelihoods through smoothing their consumption, saving their livestock, effectively managing their risks, and reducing vulnerabilities.

5.4. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following possible areas of intervention are recommended to optimize the benefits gained from the provision of micro-financial resources. These recommendations could be addressed at DECSI level, at local and regional administrations level so that stakeholders could take advantage of it and implement these recommendations.

The first four recommendations address to the DECSI, and the last two recommendation targets local and regional administration level to see livelihood improvement, poverty reduction and sustainable development in rural areas of the region.

1. Increase loan threshold

Even though the current credit improves profit, the margin is not enough to have the expected impact on the lives of rural women. It therefore recommended that microfinance institutions increase their loan threshold. An increase in loan threshold will have a greater multiplier effect on women's income through profits from income generating activities.

2. Adapt pro-poor loan interest rates

The amount of loan varies among the poor households while the amount of loan interest rate charged is the same. Loan interest rates should be charged according to the amount of loan applied for. Hence, DECSI should evaluate the current lending interest rate based on the specific socio-economic context of households. As the interest amount is additional burden to the clients thereby DECSI would be sustainable if it decreases its interest rates more that enable them to earn a better return.

3. Empowering women on credit use

The women household should be empowered and get awareness on importance of microfinance credit and how to use it and ensure that they don't have challenges in repayment due to spending the credit on consumption and non-income generating activities.

4. Diversify products and services

Currently DECSI is rendering credit services to rural households primarily for acquisition of livestock and agricultural inputs. Therefore to ensure sustainability poverty alleviation and livelihood of households particularly women, DESCi should diversify their products to widen microenterprise development efforts.

5. Give trainings focusing on women

A policy guideline may be framed at regional and local levels to evolve special formal or informal trainings focusing on women in the aspects agricultural production technology, health & sanitation, family planning and other issues to improve their managerial skill.

6. Promotion of institutional support

Regional and local administrations can extend their institutional support for client households among others by building their capacity, expand marketing opportunities, encourage investing their resources on activities that adds value to the local economy, contributes to technology transfer, improve productivity, etc.

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